

10 Years of BIMA Lifesavers - a reflective piece

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The BIMA Lifesavers program, initiated in 2013, has undergone significant evolution and progress over the course of a decade. This transformative initiative aims to impart basic life support skills within mosques.

During its inception, the BIMA Lifesavers program focused primarily on providing basic life support training in mosques. However, over the years and now in its 10th year, the program has evolved into a comprehensive and multifaceted initiative that not only teaches life-saving skills, but also emphasises community engagement and the establishment of sustainable education.

One of the noteworthy changes observed within the program is the expansion of its scope. Recognising the need to reach a broader audience, the BIMA Lifesavers program gradually extended its reach beyond local communities to encompass mosques worldwide. By forging partnerships with international organisations and leveraging digital platforms, the program has been able to transcend geographical boundaries and bring life-saving knowledge to diverse populations. Over the course of a decade, we have advanced from 3 mosques and 15 volunteers in the UK to 125 mosques and over 400 volunteers in over 12 countries worldwide.

The programme has managed to successfully deliver the event virtually for the first time during the COVID-19 pandemic, the first of its kind. In an attempt to become more feasible and accessible, Lifesavers successfully incorporated the use of 'pillow partners' instead of mannequins - apparatus developed by The Yorkshire Ambulance NHS Service, in conjunction with Resus Council UK. As a further collaboration with Resus Council UK, Lifesavers have recently finished the development of videos demonstrating basic life support in languages like Urdu to reach an even bigger population set.

This progress is a testament of the sheer dedication and commitment of all the volunteers involved. Looking forward, the BIMA Lifesavers program continues to evolve. Through continuous improvement and adaptability, we anticipate that the BIMA Lifesavers program will continue to make a profound and lasting impact on healthcare within a wide range of communities worldwide.